

METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation. *Our people believe that knowing the language is knowing the hand. In fact, English is now the most commonly spoken language on the planet. As a result, a comprehensive and systematic effort is underway in our country today to educate and teach this language. The fact that youngsters learn English from the start of their education will enable them to master multiple other languages swiftly and flawlessly in the future. As a result, the author outlines the methods and importance of teaching English in preschool education in this article.*

Keywords: *preschool, children, educator, English, Curriculum, methodology, fun games, etc.*

Foreign language abilities are becoming increasingly important in professional education today. This does not rule out the possibility of early childhood education. Teaching foreign languages to children and teenagers has become increasingly important. Learning a foreign language has become a need rather than a means of self-improvement in recent years. Foreign language study is now required not only in schools and universities, but also in a growing number of preschools. The demand for a foreign language in society, on the one hand, as well as the understanding by parents that language is not only a factor in the upbringing of modern man, but also the basis of his social and material well-being in society - on the other hand. Making this moment foreign language learning especially popular and relevant.

If knowing a foreign language was only required in certain sectors 20 years ago, it is today expected to master at least one foreign language. The age of the pupil is the most significant challenge in teaching a foreign language. It is well known that youngsters learn more easily. Until recently, teaching methods were geared toward school-aged children; now, parents are now attempting to begin learning a foreign language as soon as possible. The following are the major goals of teaching a foreign language to preschoolers:

1. Formation of basic communication skills in a foreign language in children;
2. the ability to use a foreign language to achieve their goals, to express their thoughts and feelings in the context of life communication;
3. create a positive attitude to further learning of foreign languages;

4. To arouse interest in the life and culture of other countries.

Preschool age is an excellent time to begin learning a foreign language since children of this age are sensitive to language phenomena and are interested in comprehending their speech experiences, or the "secrets" of language. The compact size of the language material is easily remembered and reproduced properly. These beneficial characteristics begin to fade with aging. Another reason why young people prefer to learn a foreign language is that it is more challenging. The less vocabulary a child has in the local language, the less speech demands he has: a tiny child's communication regions are smaller than adults', yet he still has to address difficult communication problems, which is not the case. This means that when he learns a foreign language, he does not perceive a significant difference between the possibilities in his mother tongue and those in the foreign language, and his sense of accomplishment is greater than that of older children. Teaching children is a demanding task that necessitates an entirely different methodological approach than teaching adults or schoolchildren. It is not necessary for an adult to be able to teach others a foreign language. When faced with methodologically ineffective instruction, children may develop a long-term dislike for a foreign language and lose confidence in their abilities. Working with preschoolers should only be done by experienced specialists.

The capacity of the organizer to grasp a foreign language is also important while organizing it. While learning a foreign language, every child should be encouraged to perform. They must learn to differentiate between acoustic, tactile, rhythmic, and visual stimuli. Kids are fast to organize, but also quick to forget. As a result, repeating the speech numerous times can assist youngsters remember it throughout the course of a month or through subject handouts. The classes are spiraled, and regular rehearsals are required. Teaching foreign languages effectively involves a diverse set of techniques. The major reasons for learning a language quickly are the quantity and quality of communication. During the class, students' attention should be drawn to the language's content and significance. Students should focus primarily on the content of the language. In preschool, in teaching English, children gradually develop the basics of communicative competence, which includes the following aspects in the early stages of learning English:

- the ability to repeat phonetically correctly English words behind the teacher, mother tongue or speaker, i.e. the gradual formation of auditory attention, phonetic hearing and correct pronunciation;
- mastering, combining and activating English vocabulary;
- mastering a certain amount of simple grammatical structures, composing a coherent statement.

The ability of the instructor also plays a role in successful foreign language learning. Students should be given assignments that allow them to apply what they've learned in class. Language growth requires the development of communication skills.

Students can use the language effectively through social contact, especially if they can put the meaning of the language into practice. The ability of the instructor to have meaning and negotiate for this process is one of the most important prerequisites for successful teaching. Foreign language instruction should prioritize the organization of everyday information, real knowledge, and abilities in a foreign language, but it should not overlook the acquisition of specific knowledge. If we focus on the methodological and didactic approaches used in foreign language teaching, we need to emphasize the following: The teaching process should include not only communicative, but also competencies that will allow you to apply the knowledge learned in the future.

The majority of children want to learn a foreign language. Of course, they are interested in the organization of the learning process as well as the children's ability to succeed in the learning process. It is naive to think that this interest would persist for years, thus educators must ensure that the organizers are satisfied and engaged in the course. Only if both the topics being arranged and the questions are essential, engaging, and relevant to the organizers will the content and aim of the lesson be understood and remembered. In foreign language education, foreign language organizers clash with another language, culture. As a result, it is advised to employ dependable foreign language materials, such as texts and literature that can express the same culture. Computer technology, multimedia, audio, and other information and communication tools are among the most popular ways to teach a foreign language. Individualizing education and developing motivation for preschool children's speaking activities is aided by the use of audio, video stories, fairy tales, and cognitive materials in direct educational activities. The use of ICT in the direct teaching of a foreign language develops two types of motivation: self-motivation, which is manifested by the preschool child's ability to understand the language he is learning, and motivation, which is manifested by the fact that the proposed material is interesting in itself. It brings satisfaction and builds confidence in one's own strength and strives for further improvement.

A teacher must provide clarity and an example when explaining anything. That is why English is a preschooler's game. Only by using this method can you get great outcomes and instill in the child a positive attitude toward the foreign language. Rather than studying as many lexical units as possible, forms of learning should be able to create an interest in the topic, enhance the child's communication abilities, and allow them to express themselves. It is vital to attain specific aspects of material mastery, circumstance, and meaningful use of them in the kid's competence, which will allow the child to offer a minimal amount of money to continue the development of linguistic units.

Finally, the importance of pre-school education in our children's growth cannot be overstated. We must offer them with current technology and an educational system that is up to date. Preschool education is also critical for the development of every person's roots in society, i.e., for them to grow up to be a child worthy of the

motherland and a strong person in the future. We need to pay greater attention to our children's education, establish modern environments, and assist their bodies in new ways. Foreign language organization is also crucial for children to open the door to new chances in the future, to grow into skilled professionals, and to develop as individuals who will serve society as a whole. That is why we teach our children from an early age, make them interested in reading, do not ignore every child in our society, deal with children with disabilities, attract their attention with various fun games, regularly encourage them to learn foreign languages. We will not be mistaken in saying that it will be a step.

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